

YOUTH CRIME: THE MAIN PROBLEMS AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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Currently, protecting young people from various threats of the modern world is considered one of the most important tasks of the state. The current youth is the largest generation in terms of number and accounts for 60% of the total population of the country, namely more than 19 million.

The reforms carried out over the past five years in the field of preventing youth crime in the country have significantly reduced crime. But unfortunately, according to the statistics of 2023, it was noted that every third person who committed a crime is a young man. Almost 3,600 minors committed crimes in 2023. In five years, this figure has grown 4.4 times. The number of extortion cases increased by 70% over the year, hooliganism - by 60%, intentional grievous bodily harm - by 40%, rape and attempted murder - by 20%.

In 2023, 3,599 minors (13-17 years old) who committed crimes were registered in Uzbekistan. This is 15.6% more than a year earlier (3,112) and 40% more than in 2021 (2,595).

According to the above statistics, it is obvious that the reforms in this area are not yielding positive results. The issue of the effectiveness of reforms in the field of youth crime prevention is complex and multifaceted. Some reforms may show positive results, while others may be less successful. Therefore, several reasons for the inefficiency of the reforms should be considered:

- insufficient funding and resources;
- lack of a comprehensive approach;
- failure to take into account the specifics of local conditions;
- insufficient involvement of stakeholders;
- insufficient assessment and monitoring.

Successful reforms in the field of youth crime prevention require careful planning, resources, involvement of all stakeholders and an integrated approach to solving the problem.

The very concept of unorganized criminal activity of youth is a form of crime that is not controlled or coordinated by some organized criminal association or structure. Unlike organized crime, which is usually characterized by a well-organized organization, clear hierarchical structures and activities, unorganized criminal activity is most often carried out individually or in small groups that do not have a clear organizational structure.

Such criminal activity may include various types of crimes such as theft, robbery, drug and alcohol offenses, property damage, fights and other forms of violations of the law. These actions can be motivated by various factors, including social, economic and psychological aspects.

Disorganized criminal activity of young people can be caused by various reasons, such as the desire to earn money, the search for adrenaline, social recognition within their group or community, as well as the lack of prospects for a better future or alternative ways of realization. This is a serious problem that requires attention from society and the State in order to provide support and opportunities for young people, as well as to prevent their involvement in criminal activities.

Disorganized criminal activity among young people is often associated with a number of factors, including social, economic and psychological aspects. The main reasons why young people may be inclined to such activities:

- social factors (lack of social support, low level of education, lack of access to quality health services and social assistance can lead to the emergence of crime among young people);
- economic factors (high youth unemployment, low income, insufficient access to education and employment opportunities may contribute to the involvement of young people in illegal types of earnings);
- psychological factors (low self-esteem, lack of prospects for the future, the desire to attract attention or recognition, as well as problems in the family or personal life can stimulate young people to criminal activity);
- the impact of the environment (presence in a society where crime has flourished can have a strong impact on young people, forcing them to repeat the behavior of peers or even older people);
- lack of prospects and alternatives (if young people do not see alternative ways to realize and achieve success, they may turn to crime as a way of survival or to achieve their goals).

In order to combat unorganized crime among young people, it is important to provide them with access to education, vocational training, social support and employment opportunities. In addition, it is necessary to create crime prevention programs, including information campaigns, social projects and cooperation with local communities.

To summarize, it should be noted that youth crime is a multifaceted problem that includes many social, economic, psychological and cultural aspects. Conducting dissertation research in the field of unorganized criminal activity

among young people is a common practice in the academic community. Several topics are proposed that could be studied within the framework of dissertations: the influence of the social environment on the formation of criminal behavior among young people (research of factors such as family environment, education, peer relations and media on criminal behavior of young people); the effectiveness of youth crime prevention programs (analysis of various programs and activities aimed at preventing disorganized criminal activity among young people, and assessment of their effectiveness); psychological aspects of youth crime (study of psychological mechanisms and factors influencing the involvement of youth in criminal activity, such as low self-esteem, desire for recognition, aggressive behavior, etc.); the role of education and vocational training in preventing youth crime (study of the impact of education, vocational training and access to employment on the crime rate among young people); comparative analysis of youth crime in different countries (comparative study of factors influencing youth crime in different CIS countries or between the CIS and other regions).

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